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Research

Causes for Prosperity of *Sāsana* (Admonition) and Causes of its Downfall

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Abstract: *Sāsana* is admonition. In the dispensation of the Buddha there are *Pariyatti Sāsana* – learning and teaching of *Piṭaka* literatures treatises, *Paṭipatti Sāsana* – practice according to the admonition or practice of two *bhāvanā* and *Paṭivedha Sāsana* – insight into the realization of four noble truths (*sacca*). Buddha's *Sāsana* is endowed with the following qualities: leading to the benefits of god, man and sentient beings, be happy and wealthy, devoid of passion '*rāga*', insight into the suffering, and to be liberated from all the traps of defilements (*kilesā*). Many causes leading to downfall of such a kind of *Sāsana* are: gradual diminishing of *Pariyatti Sāsana*, *Paṭipatti Sāsana*, *Paṭivedha Sāsana*, gradual fading out of the form of monk called *Liṅga Sāsana*, total disappearance of the relics of the Buddha and disciples called *Dhātu Sāsana*, not listening to the *Dhamma*, longing of gain by monks, and dispute and quarrelling of monks. Similarly, there are many causes leading to the prosperity of *Sāsana*. This paper explores the causes leading to the prosperity and downfall of *Sāsana* by studying some of the discourses taught by the Buddha.

Keywords : *admonition, discourse, prosperity, downfall.*

Introduction

Sāsana denotes admonition (should be followed). The dispensation of the Buddha was established based on the three fundamental things, namely, morality (*sīla*), concentration (*samādhi*), and wisdom (*paññā*). It is found in the *dhamma* delivered by the Buddha that the *Sāsana* is good at the beginning by means of morality (*sīla*), good at the middle by means of concentration (*samādhi*), and good at the end by means of wisdom (*paññā*).

Moreover, the Buddha's *Sāsana* is endowed with five incomparable attributes, namely, being noble, clean and devoid of impurities, not mixed with evil deeds, able to be realized, and necessary to be controlled much. Practicing in the Buddha's dispensation, realization of suffering insightfully, devoid of passion (*rāga*), free from lust by abandoning of

cankers (*kilesā*) and practicing the noble practices leading to reach *Nibbāna* would be fulfilled.

There are many causes for the prosperity of Buddha *Sāsana* that leading to get many benefits as well as the causes for its downfall. With regard to these causes of prosperity and downfall of the *Sāsana* the Buddha had delivered the facts that should be conducted and avoided by giving many similes. These would be selected from these teachings (*desanā*) and explored briefly in this paper.

Meaning of *Sāsana*

The word *sāsanā* is *sāsana* ($\sqrt{\text{ssa}} + \text{yu}$)¹ and having the meaning of admonition, news, and promulgation of authority. Moreover, it is explained as words of admonishment.² The dispensation of the Buddha has three kinds of *Sāsana*. These are as follows.

1. *Pariyatti Sāsana*³ studying of *Piṭaka* literatures
2. *Paṭipatti Sāsana*⁴ practice according to the admonishment or practicing of two kinds of *bhāvanā*
3. *Paṭivedha Sāsana*⁵ realization of four noble truths (*sacca*)

Moreover, *Piṭaka* is divided into three.⁶ These are as follows.

1. *Yathāparādha Sāsana* Vinaya *Piṭaka*, admonishing of the sinner according to his fault
2. *Yathānuloma Sāsana* Suttanta *Piṭaka*, admonishing according to the temperament of sentient beings
3. *Yathādhamma Sāsana* Abhidhamma *Piṭaka*, admonishing of individual, being, water, earth, forest, mountain with regard to materiality (*rūpa*) and mentality (*nāma*).

Benefits of Practicing in *Sāsana*

Regarding with the practicing in *Sāsana*, the wandering ascetics (*paribbājaka*) having the view other than the *Sāsana* asked the monks for what benefits to get by practicing in the dispensation of the Buddha in the *Sambahulabhi Sutta*⁷, *Gilānavagga*, *Salāyatana Saṃyutta*. Monks asked about this fact to the Buddha and the Buddha answered that practicing in the *Sāsana* in order to realize insightfully into the suffering. Either arising of feeling (*vedanā*) of happiness (*sukha*), unsatisfactory (*dukkha*), or equanimity (*upekkhā*) due to touching of visible object with eye (*cakkhusamphassa*) or consciousness (*citta*), indeed, are suffering. So

¹ Pāmyandhan, 1031.

² Dī, 2, 42.

³ Apa, ṭṭha, 1, 256.

⁴ Thera, ṭṭha, 1, 276.

⁵ Sī, ṭī, thit, 1. 45.

⁶ Illustration, 618.

⁷ Saṃ, 2, 277.

the Buddha taught monks to answer that in order to realize and insight into the suffering practicing the noble practice in the dispensation of the Buddha.

Moreover, the Buddha caused his follower monks to answer by asking of wandering ascetics (*paribbājaka*) having the view other than the Buddhist view that monks are practicing in the Buddha *Sāsanā* in order to have the benefit of extinguishing of passion (*rāga*) and the path leading to be void of passion is noble path (*ariyamagga*) having the eight characteristics. That noble path is a practice leading to be void of passion.⁸

The Buddha continued to deliver in the *Uruvelavagga*,⁹ *Pathamaṇṇāsaka*, *Catukkanipāta*, *Aṅguttara Nikāya* to the monks that practicing of noble practice in the dispensation does not mean to persuade people by showing wonders, wishing for gain and fame. However, for controlling, abandoning of cankers (*kilesā*), devoid of and extinguishing of lust and passion (*rāga*), and achieving of *Nibbāna*.

With regard to practicing in dispensation Shin *Sāriputtara* was asked by *Sāmaṇḍhakāni Thera* that what is suffering and happiness in this *Dhamma Vinaya Sāsana* when Shin *Sāriputtara* was residing at the *Nālaka Village* in *Magadha*. At that time Shin *Sāriputtara* answered that if there is no delight in the dispensation there will be suffering and if delight in the dispensation there will be happiness. If there is no delighting it will lead to have suffering in any posture, such as, walking, standing, sitting, and lying either in village or forest or at the foot of a tree and if there is delighting the happiness and calmness is achieved.¹⁰

Causes Leading to the Prosperity of *Sāsana*

The Buddha delivered the causes leading to the prosperity of *Sāsana* in many discourses (*Sutta*). There the Buddha taught that the showing correctly the offences concerning with monk is one of the cause leading to the prosperity of *Sāsanā*.¹¹ The Buddha continued to teach that learning the discourses that should be learnt with right wording and letter, easy to be admonished, having vast knowledge and remembering the Dhamma and Vinaya by heart and teach other, not trying to have abundance in property by elders monks, practicing threefold training (*sikkhā*) fully, and ardent in practicing of *Jhāna*, *magga*, *phala* for the realization of *Nibbāna*. These are the causes leading to the prosperity of *Sāsana* taught by the Buddha.¹²

⁸ Saṃ, 3, 21-2.

⁹ Añ, 1, 334.

¹⁰ Añ, 3, 351.

¹¹ Añ, 1, 20-1.

¹² Añ, 1, 456.

Paying respect of monks, nuns, male and female lay devotees in the Buddha, the Dhamma, the Saṅgha, training (*sikkhā*), and concentration (*samādhi*) is included as one of the causes leading to the prosperity of *Sāsana*.¹³ The Buddha delivered that *Sāsana* would be prosperous if being endowed with having faith (*saddhā*), morality (*sīla*), having vast knowledge, easy to be admonished, having good friend, having effort, having mindfulness (*sati*), being contented, having little desire, and having right view in the Ānanda Sutta, *Theravagga, Dasaka Nipāta, Aṅguttara Nikāya*.¹⁴

Moreover, the Buddha said that practicing of four foundation of mindfulness (*satipaṭṭhāna*): contemplation of the body (*kāyānupassana*), contemplation of feeling (*vedanānupassana*), contemplation of the consciousness (*cittānupassana*), and contemplation of the dhamma (*dhammānupassana*) repeatedly is the cause for long lasting of *Sāsana* as well.¹⁵ Again, Shin Mahā Kassapa taught to his pupil monks that they should abandon the following ten kinds: having ill-will (*abhijjhā*), hatred (*dosa*), sloth and torpor (*thinamiddha*), restlessness (*uddhacca*), skeptical doubt (*vicikicchā*), delight in new *kamma*, delight in talking, delight in sleeping, delight in associating with people, stop to practice only getting a little advance with the things what should be done, and thought of fail in practicing.¹⁶

Shin Mahā Moggallāna, the left-hand chief disciple of the Buddha delivered that through abandoning of the following ten kinds of *dhamma*: hatred, vie with one another, being grudge, envy, cunning, deception, having ill-will, and thinking of having reached to the end despite of having little *dhamma* that should need to do more, the Buddha's *Dhamma Vinaya Sāsana* would reach to the prosperity.¹⁷ The Buddha had already been free from the trap of defilements (*kilesā*) by himself and sent his disciple monks to conduct missionary for prosperity of *Sāsana* in order for the benefits of all sentient beings. The Buddha instructed the missionary monks to travel for the benefit of gods and men, not to go together in a single voyage, deliver the *dhamma* which is good at the beginning, middle, and at the end characterized with full meaning and grammar, and deliver the practice having complete purity and nobility. Besides, the Buddha himself went to the Senanigara from Uruvela to deliver those were able to understand the *dhamma* with wisdom eye having little mist of cankers (*kilesā*) as they were unbeneficial because of lacking in listening to the *Dhamma*.¹⁸

¹³ Saṃ, 1, 422.

¹⁴ Añ, 3, 377.

¹⁵ Saṃ, 3, 149-51.

¹⁶ Añ, 3, 387.

¹⁷ Añ, 3, 380.

¹⁸ Vi, 3, 27.

Because of the sending of missionary by the Buddha leading not only to the increase in development of the community of the Order (*Samgha*) but also arising of foremost laity devotees in *Sāsana*. Of these people the male devotees to whom the Buddha conferred the title of pre-eminent (*etadagga*), such as, Taphussa, Bhallika, Anāthapiṇḍika, Citta the rich man, Hatthaka Āḷāvaka, Mahānāma, Uggata the rich man, Uggata the rich man, Sūrabandha, Jīvaka, and Nakulapitā were famous. In the same way, Sujātā, Visākhā, Khujjuttarā, Sāmāvatī, Uttarā, Uppavāsā, Suppiya, Kātiyānī, Nakulamātā, and Kālī Upāsikā were well-known.¹⁹

Causes Leading to the Downfall of *Sāsana*

The Buddha had delivered the causes leading to the prosperity of *Sāsana* and causes leading to the downfall of *Sāsana* as well. The Buddha admonished in the *Aṅguttara Nikāya*, *Ekakanipāta*, *Anāpattivagga*²⁰ with regard to monks that stating of non-offence (*anāpatti*) as offence (*āpatti*), trivial offence as grievous offence, grievous offence as trivial offence, offence that could not be amended as offence that could be amended, and offence that should not be amended as offence that should be amended means those monks causing to be unbeneficial of gods and men and to suffer, arising of unwholesome *dhamma* and disappearance of *Sāsana*.

The Buddha taught the following are the causes leading to the disappearance of *Sāsana* in the *Suṇāvīnaya Sutta*, *Indriyavagga*, *Catutthapaṇṇāsaka*, *Aṅguttara Nikāya*. Having learnt the bad words and teach the bad words and letter, difficult to admonish, not teaching others though having vast knowledge and able to remember the *dhamma* and *vinaya* by heart, trying to have abundance of gain by elder monks, negligence in threefold training (*sikkhā*), irresponsible in three *viveka*: *kāyaviveka*²¹, *cittaviveka*²², *upadhiviveka*²³, not practicing of to achieve *Jhāna*, path (*magga*) and fruition attainment (*phala*) in order to realize *Nibbāna*, and following the foot step of elder monks' practice by later generation. These are the causes leading to the disappearance of *Sāsana*.

The Buddha said to Shin Ānandā in the *Ānanda Sutta*²⁴, *Theravagga*, *Dutiyapaṇṇāsaka*, *Dasakanipāta*, *Aṅguttara Nikāya* that if monks were lacking in faith (*saddhā*), no morality (*sīla*), little knowledge, difficult to admonish, having bad friend, being

¹⁹ Añ, 1, 27-8.

²⁰ Añ, 3, 20-1.

²¹ Kāyaviveka - aloof from five sensual pleasures (*kāmaguṇa*)

²² Cittaviveka - aloof from unwholesome *dhamma* (*akusaladhamma*)

²³ Upadhiviveka - entering in the fruition attainment (*pahalasamāpatti*) taking *Nibbāna* as object

²⁴ Añ, 3, 377.

idle, without mindfulness, not contented, having ill-will, and having wrong view the *Dhamma Vinaya Sāsana* would not flourish and not be prosperous.

The Buddha said to Shin *Mahā Kassapa* in the *Saddhammapatirūpaka Sutta*²⁵ that not respecting of the five things, namely, the Buddha, the *Dhamma*, the *Samgha*, training (*sikkhā*) and concentration (*samādhi*) by monks, nuns, male lay devotee, and female lay devotee leads to the disappearance of *Sāsana*. Regarding with the downfall of *Sāsana*, the Buddha said that the virtuous *dhamma* cannot be last long well after the demise of the Buddha (*parinibbāna*) by not practicing of four foundation of mindfulness (*satipaṭṭhāna dhamma*) and practicing repeatedly.²⁶

Moreover, Shin *Mahā Kassapa* delivered to the monks that those who are covetous (*abhijjhā*), angry, sloth and torpor (*thinamiddha*), restless, skeptical doubt, delight in new *kamma*, fond of accompanied with associates, and thinking of having reached to the end despite of having little *dhamma* that should need to do more cause the diminishing of *Sāsana*.²⁷

Shin Mahā Moggallāna, the left-hand chief disciple of the Buddha taught his pupil monks that in this dispensation taking grudge, not to recognize other's gratitude, vie with one another, envy, cunning, deception, having ill-will, and thinking of having reached to the end despite of having little *dhamma* that should need to do more are the causes for the diminishing and disappearance of *Sāsana*.²⁸

Five Causal *Dhamma* for the Disappearance of *Sāsana*

There are five causal *dhamma* for the disappearance of *Sāsana*.²⁹ These are as follows.

1. Disappearance of *Pariyatti Sāsana*, gradually disappearing of three *Piṭakas*
2. Disappearance of *Paṭipatti Sāsana*, diminishing and disappearance of good practices that lead

to achieve *Jhāna*, *vipassanā*, path and fruition attainment

3. Disappearance of *Paṭivedha Sāsana*, not arising of those having path and fruition attainment

(*magga*, *phala*), knowledge of *Paṭisambhidāvijjā*, and supernormal knowledge (*abhiññāṇa*)

²⁵ Sam, 1, 422.

²⁶ Sam, 3, 149-51.

²⁷ Añ, 3, 378.

²⁸ *Ibid*, 380.

²⁹ Illustration, 618.

4. Disappearance of *Liṅga Sāsana*, diminishing in characteristic appearance of monk bearing eight kinds of requisites (*parikkharā*) gradually such as not to take alms bowl, lower robe, double robe, bearing only the piece of cloth in the ear lobe, and finally discard all.
5. Disappearance of *Dhātu Sāsana*, disappearance of relics of the Buddha and the disciples due to the lacking of veneration and adoration by anyone (*Dhātuparinibbāna*).

The Buddha had delivered the causes for the disappearance of *Sāsana* and all the dangers would arise mostly depending on *Vajjiputtaka*.³⁰ Moreover, Ven. Devadatta was well-known as one who disturbed the *Sāsana* during the time of the Buddha. Ven. Devadatta was a brother-in-law of the Buddha he had been suffering from vomiting blood for nine month because he had made schism of *Samgha* and tried to kill the Buddha with various means thinking of him to be the Buddha. Finally, he was made to bring him before the Buddha by carrying with a small couch but he was swallowed up by the earth and fell into the *Avīci* hell near the small lake of Jetavana monastery in Sāvatti as he had not done the good deed to venerate the Buddha.³¹

Conclusion

The Buddha had fulfilled the perfection (*pāramī*) for four *asaṅkhyeyya* and a hundred thousand aeons in order to attain Omniscience (*Sabbaññutañāṇa*) for the benefits of all beings. Those who follow and practice the dispensation of the Buddha can attain many mundane (*lokiya*) and supra-mundane benefits as it is full of all causes. It is found that in the Buddha's *Sāsana*, among monks, Shin Sāriputtarā and Shin Mahā Moggallāna, of lay male devotees, the rich man Citta and the rich man Hatthaka Āḷāvaka, of female disciples bhikkhunī Khemā and bhikkhunī Uppalavaṇa, of female lay devotees Khujjhuttarā and Nandamātā the citizen of Veḷakaṇḍakī City were the model individuals worthy to be emulated.

The Buddha taught and instructed for monks having faith in *Sāsana* and delighting in the dispensation. It is found that the Buddha had admonished his disciples for the purity of *Sāsana* that the men of good family who have known the benefits of themselves and others should be completed and not to forget in doing wholesome deeds (*kusala*). The Buddha taught that if monks practice well the world will not be void of Arahant to his last disciple (*pacchimasāvaka*), Subhadda the wandering ascetic (*paribbājaka*) when the Buddha was about to enter *Parinibbāna*. Delivering in this way by the Buddha is found the intention of

³⁰ Vi, 1, 27.

³¹ Dhamma, t̥ṭha, 1, 95-6.

the Buddha for lasting long of the Buddha's *Sāsana*. Only then the Buddha *Sāsana* will be established well and firmly for a long time.

The Buddha had been tried hard for the benefits of all men, gods, Brahmas, and beings from the time of his enlightenment to the entering of *parinibbāna* with any failure. These actions carried out and teaching such as *Dhamma* and *Vinaya* still exist as the Buddha's admonishing *Sāsana*. The Buddha *Sāsana* causes those who practicing will be extinguishing of mental defilements (*kilesā*), to reach the end of the path and fruition attainment, the way leading to attain *Nibbāna*, and peace and calm for the world. By means of convening the Buddhist synods and practicing according to the admonishing of the Buddha unanimously the invaluable *Sāsana* should be protected and maintained.

Abbreviations

Añ, 1	Aṅguttara Pāḷi (ekaka, duka, tika, catukkanipāta)
Añ, 3	Aṅguttara Pāḷi (aṭṭhaka, navaka, dasaka, ekādasakanipāta)
Apa, ṭṭha, 1	Apadānaṭṭhakathā (paṭhamobhāgo)
Thera, ṭṭha, 1	Theragāthāṭṭhakathā (paṭhamobhāgo)
Dī, 2	Mahāvagga Pāḷi
Dhamma, ṭṭha, 1	Dhammapadaaṭṭhakathā (paṭhamobhāgo)
Pāmyandhan	Pāḷi Myanmar Dictionary
Milinda	Milindapañhā Pāḷi,
Vi, 1	Pārājikaṇḍa Pāḷi
Vi, 3	Mahāvagga Pāḷi
Visuddhi, 1	Visuddhimaggo (paṭhamobhāgo)
Sam, 1	Sagāthāvagga and Nidānavagga Saṃyutta Pāḷi
Sam, 2	Khandhavagga and Saḷāyatanavagga Saṃyutta Pāḷi
Sam, 3	Mahāvagga Saṃyutta Pāḷi
Illustration	Research illustration Dictionary
Sī, tī, thit, 1	Sīlakkhandhavagga Abhinavaṭṭikā (ṭīkāthit) First volume

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